

R29,20

6x60°

6xM3x0.5

Ø 63,50

SECTION C-C

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

Gérard Zinzindhoué Project

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE	
DRAWN				
CHK'D				
APPV'D				
MFG				
Q.A				

TITLE:

UW-Front_Glass_03

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:1

SHEET 1 OF 1